

THE EFFECT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE COGNITIVE ABILITY OF STUDENTS

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ANNOTATION

Students' cognitive impairments significantly affect their ability to master subjects. It was observed that the wide use of information technologies in the life of students causes cognitive disorders. Being in the area of mobile phone, computer, wi-fi and the duration of sleep were studied and the impact on students' cognitive activity was studied.

Key words: cognitive disorders in students, information communication technologies, neuropsychological tests.

The urgency of the problem. Students are a forward-thinking, active intellectual and physical part of the society, and their use of information and communication technologies in the course of studying and scientific research is much higher than some layers of the society. The presence of students in an area close to information and communication technologies for longer periods of time can cause various levels of cognitive disorders in students.

The purpose of the study : to study the relationship between the time of communication of students with different information technologies and cognitive disorders observed in students.

Research materials and methods. The results of examination and analysis of 122 students of the Bukhara State Medical Institute in 2023-2024 were presented in order to solve the scientific goals and tasks envisaged by our research work. Students were divided into 3 groups according to the length of time they use mobile phones and computers. The first group consists of students who use these devices up to 5 hours a day, the second group consists of students who use them 5-10 hours a day, and the 3rd group consists of students who use these devices for more than 10 hours.

Analysis and results. In subjective, objective, laboratory and instrumental examinations of all three groups, the symptoms of somatic diseases were denied, the levels of cognitive disorders, the frequency and duration of the pains of the first group of the first group during the week were studied. From the

anamnesis, the frequency of acute respiratory diseases in the first group and its relationship with the duration of using information technologies were studied.

In the first group $n=21$, the time of using information technology is 4.3 ± 1.4 hours, in the second group $n=60$, 7.9 ± 1.6 hours and in the third group $n=41$, 14.2 ± 1.7 hours did (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Figure 1. The average time indicators of students of the first group of research groups using information technologies

Among the research groups, the first group of students spends a different part of their time on using information technologies, the number of students involved in the research was 17% in the first group, 49% in the second group, and 34% in the third group (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Indicators of attention disorders based on the Landolt test

In the first group of students, when attention disorders in students were studied using the Landolt test 14.3% had no attention disorder, 23.8% had mild attention disorder, 48.3% had moderate attention disorder, and 14.3% had

severe attention disorder. In the second group, 11.7% had no attention disorders, 23.3% had mild attention disorders, 48.3% had moderate attention disorders, and 16.7% had severe attention disorders, while the third group had no attention disorders, 9.8%, mild attention disorder 22% and moderate attention disorder 48.8% and severe attention disorder 31.7%. When the research groups were analyzed, it was shown that the more time students spend with information technology, the more pronounced attention disorders in them.

Conclusion: In all three groups, as a result of the increase in the time of working with information technologies, there was a positive correlation between cognitive functions, quick memory and attention disorder indicators.

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